

DELAMINATION ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES IN DRILLING AND QUASI-STATIC PENETRATION

Navid Zarif Karimi¹, Parnian Kianfar² and Giangiacomo Minak³

¹Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Bologna
40 Fontanelle Ave., 47100, Forli, Italy
Email: navid.zarif@unibo.it, web page: <http://www.unibo.it>

²Department of Biomedical Engineering, Amirkabir University of Technology
424 Hafez Ave., 15914, Tehran, Iran
Email: parnian.kianfar@aut.ac.ir, web page: <http://www.aut.ac.ir>

³Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Bologna
40 Fontanelle Ave., 47100, Forli, Italy
Email: giangiacomo.minak@unibo.it, web page: <http://www.unibo.it>

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ABSTRACT

Drilling of composite materials is highly important from aspects of operation capacity and safety of structures; especially because these materials are mostly used in transportation industry. One of the main damages observed after drilling composite materials is the delamination, which refers to a damage bonder around the machined holes. This type of damage causes poor assembly tolerance, reduce the structural integrity and has the potential for long-term performance deterioration under fatigue loads. Drilling-induced delamination occurs both at the entry and the exit of the drilled holes and accounts for 60% of all part rejections during final assembly of composite products. In this paper, the effect of machining parameters, feed rate and cutting speed, on delamination in drilling process and quasi-static penetration were investigated. For this purpose, two sets of experiments, drilling and quasi static penetration, were designed based on full factorial design. Using analysis of variance, optimum cutting condition for minimum delamination was determined. A correlation between feed rate and cutting speed with the delamination factor was established by second order linear regression. According to the results, delamination increases with feed rate; whereas it decreases with cutting speed. Finally, a comparison between the delamination in drilling process and quasi-static penetration by conical-nosed projectile was made. According to the results, the difference is significant so that the average value of delamination for each level in quasi-static penetration is about two times greater than drilling process.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, increasing demand in a variety of industries for high-performance and lightweight structures have stimulated a strong expanding development of fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composite laminates. Because of their superior properties such as high specific strength and stiffness, high corrosion resistance and weight saving, they are being used to replace conventional metallic materials [1, 2].

As structural materials, joining composite laminates to other metal material structures could not be avoided. Bolt joining efficiency and quality depend on the quality of machined holes. Various drilling methods are used such as conventional drilling, ultrasonic drilling, laser-beam drilling and water jet drilling for a variety of economic and quality reasons. For rivets and bolted joints, damaged-free and precise holes must be drilled in the components to ensure high joint strength and precision. However, some special characteristics of composite laminates such as non-homogeneous, anisotropic, and highly abrasive and hard reinforced fibers result in them difficult to machine. Moreover, several undesirable damages, including delamination, matrix cracking and fiber breakage, induced by drilling severely

reduce strength against fatigue [3-5].

Among the problems caused by drilling, delamination is considered as the most critical. It was reported that, in aircraft industry, the rejection of parts consist of composite laminates due to drilling-induced delamination during final assembly was as high as 60% [6]. Thus, any drilling-induced delamination resulting in the rejection of components represents an expensive loss since drilling is often a final machining operation during assembly of components. In order to overcome these difficulties it is essential to select appropriate cutting parameters owing to the fact that an unsuitable choice could lead to a catastrophe.

Delamination occurs due to localized bending in the zone sited at the point of drill contact. El-Sonbaty et al. [7] identified two forms of delamination called peel-up at the drill entrance and push-down at the exit side of the work piece. Peel-up occurs as the drill enters the laminate. After the cutting edge of the drill makes contact with the laminate, the cutting force acting in the peripheral direction is the driving force for delamination. It generates a peeling force in the axial direction through the slope of the drill flute results in separating the laminas from each other, at the top, forming a delamination zone. The peeling force is a function of tool geometry and friction between the tool and workpiece. Push-out is the delamination mechanism occurring as the drill reaches the exit side of the material, where the uncut thickness smaller and the resistance to deformation decrease. At some point the loading exceeds the interlaminar bond strength and delamination occurs. This happens before the laminate is completely penetrated by the drill. A different drill geometry and cutting conditions can reduce the delamination by lowering the thrust force. In practice, it has been found that the delamination associated with push-out is more severe than that of peel-up.

In order to quantitatively evaluate the amount of delamination, Chen [8] proposed an approach to obtain the value of the conventional delamination factor as shown in Eq. (1). The conventional delamination factor is not appropriated owing to the fact that the crack size does not represent the damage magnitude conveniently. Furthermore, this procedure does not indicate the damage area. Davim et al. [9] proposed a novel approach to measure the delamination factor which is called the adjusted delamination factor and calculated through Eq. (2). The first part of Eq. (2) represents the size of the crack contribution and the second part represents the damage area contribution.

$$F_{da} = \frac{D_{max}}{D_0} \quad (1)$$

$$F_{da} = \alpha \frac{D_{max}}{D_0} + \beta \frac{A_{max}}{A_0} \quad (2)$$

The coefficients α and β can be calculated from Eq. (3).

$$\beta = \frac{A_d}{A_0 - A_{max}} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha = 1 - \beta \quad (3)$$

Where D_0 is the nominal diameter of the hole, D_{max} is the maximum diameter of the damage hole, A_0 is the area related to the nominal hole, A_{max} is the area related to the maximum diameter of the delamination zone and A_d is the delaminated area.

Until now many researchers have attempted to minimize the delamination on drilled components of composite materials, considering the speed, feed and point angle as the affecting parameters with various methods such as Taguchi, multi-objective optimization, neural network, genetic algorithm, etc. [10-18]. Isik et al. [19] proposed an approach to select cutting parameters for damage factor in drilling of glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRPs). They investigated the influence of drilling parameters on surface quality of woven GFRP plastic composite material. They showed that by increasing of cutting speed, damage factor decreases at both hole entrance and exit; whereas, it increases as the feed rate increases. Velayudham et al. [20] studied the effect of point geometry and their influence on thrust and delamination in drilling of polymeric composites. Their results show that drill point has considerable influence on thrust and delamination and tripod point geometry produce the least delamination damage. Krishnamoorthy et al. [21] used Taguchi method and grey fuzzy analysis for the optimization

of drilling parameters for CFRP composites with multiple performance characteristics. Grey fuzzy optimization of drilling parameters was based on five different output performance characteristics, namely, thrust force, torque, entry delamination, exit delamination and eccentricity of the holes. They used analysis of variance (ANOVA) to find the percentage contribution of the drilling parameters and found that feed rate is the most influential factor in drilling of CFRP composites. In a similar work, Palanikumar [18] proposed an effective approach for the optimization of drilling parameters with multiple performance characteristics based on the Taguchi method with grey relational analysis. Based on the results, the order of the importance for the controllable factors grade is feed rate followed by spindle speed. Zhou et al. [22, 23] investigated the response of woven Kevlar/polyester laminates to quasi-static and dynamic penetration by cylindro-conical projectiles with an apex of primarily 60 degrees for various laminate constructions, target thicknesses and impact speeds. In order to determine the effect of tool geometry, tools with diameter of 12.7, 6.35 and 3.175 mm with vertex angle of 60, 90, 120 degrees were used. According to the results, the initial slope for different diameters is about the same; but the peak force is roughly proportional to the diameter of the projectile. Moreover, the initial slopes for the 60, 90 and 120 degrees tips are almost the same because global deflections dominate at this stage. The peak force increases with tip angle. The effect of back-up plate was also studied. The peak load for the supported and unsupported cases is about the same, but the restrained system exhibits a much lower deflection both at the maximum load and at complete perforation. In a similar work, Goldsmith et al. [24] found similar results for partial and complete perforation of woven carbon fiber/epoxy laminates with thick-nesses ranging from 1.3 to 6.6 mm by 60 degrees cylindro-conical hard steel strikers at normal under both quasi-static and dynamic condition.

In this paper, the effect of machining parameters, feed rate and spindle speed, on delamination in drilling process and quasi-static penetration are investigated. For this purpose, two sets of experiments, drilling and quasi static penetration, are designed based on full factorial design. Finally, a comparison between the delamination in drilling process and quasi-static penetration by conical-nosed projectile is made.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Means and materials

The composite laminates were manufactured by hand lay-up technique. The laminates were made of araldite LY556 epoxy resin reinforced with high strength E-glass woven fiber. The properties of the epoxy resin are as follows: density of 1.12 g/cm³, ultimate tensile strength of 80 MPa, failure strain of 3% and elastic modulus of 2.7 GPa. The woven fabric has a density of 292 g/m², ultimate tensile strength of 2150 MPa and elastic modulus of 74 GPa. The GFRP laminates were approximately 5 mm thick consisting of 16 plies and had an approximately 60% fiber weight fraction. After preparation, specimens of size 100 × 100 mm were cut on a water-cooled diamond table saw.

All drilling tests were performed on an FP4M vertical machining (maximum rpm, 2500 and feed rate, 200 mm/min). An appropriate clamping system was employed to fix the specimens in the drilling machine. The standard HSS twist drills of 5 mm diameter with 30° helix angle were used for the experimental program. To avoid tool wear, the tool was changed after each experiment and no coolant was used in any of the drilling experiments. The holes were generated at the center of the specimen and each experiment was replicated three times.

2.2 Plan of experiments

Drilling experiments were planned based on general full factorial design. By full factorial design, we mean that in each complete trial or replication of the experiment all possible combinations of the levels of the factors are investigated. In some experiments, the difference in response between the levels of on factor is not the same at all levels of the other factors. When this occurs, there is an interaction between the factors. Factorial designs are more efficient than one-factor-at-a-time experiments. A factorial design is necessary when interactions may be present to avoid misleading conclusions. Furthermore, factorial designs allow the effects off a factor to be estimated at several levels of the other factors, yielding conclusions that are valid over a range of experimental conditions.

Minitab16 was used to create the design matrix and analyze the results as statistical software. Two factors i.e. feed rate and spindle speed at three levels were used as input factors and delamination factor was considered as the main response factor. Input factors and their corresponding levels are given in Table 1.

	Feed rate (mm/min)	Spindle speed (rpm)
Drilling	31.5-63-125	315-630-1000
Quasi-static penetration	31.5-63-125	-

Table 1: Input factors and their corresponding levels.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The measured adjusted delamination factor (F_{da}) for drilling process and quasi-static penetration are reported in in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively.

Test No.	Parameters		F_{da} (replicates)		
	Feed rate (mm/min)	Spindle speed (rpm)	1	2	3
1	31.5	315	1.09	1.10	1.08
2	31.5	630	1.10	1.07	1.08
3	31.5	1000	1.07	1.04	1.05
4	63	315	1.12	1.13	1.11
5	63	630	1.15	1.15	1.12
6	63	1000	1.10	1.11	1.15
7	125	315	1.18	1.19	1.17
8	125	630	1.15	1.16	1.13
9	125	1000	1.13	1.08	1.11

Table 2: The measured experiment results for drilling process.

Test No.	Parameters	F_{da} (replicates)		
	Feed rate (mm/min)	1	2	3
1	31.5	2.15	1.95	2.25
2	63	2.25	2.18	2.10
3	125	2.4	2.16	2.28

Table 3: The measured experimental results for quasi-static penetration.

The complete analysis of variance is shown in Table 4. According to the P-value column, feed rate and spindle speed significantly affect the delamination factor at the 95% confidence level. The feed rate-spindle speed interaction has a P-value of 0.023, indicating interaction between these factors. To assist in the practical interpretation of this experiment, it is helpful to construct a graph of average responses at each treatment combination. This graph is shown in Fig. 1. According to the slope of the feed rate and spindle speed curves, delamination increases with feed rate, whereas, it decreases with spindle speed. The order of the importance for the parameters is feed rate (56.8%) followed by spindle speed (15.9%). Moreover, the significant interaction is indicated by the lack of parallelism of the lines.

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F ₀	P-Value	Contribution Percentage (%)
Feed rate	0.0230222	2	0.0115111	39.34	0.0001	56.8
Spindle Speed	0.0068667	2	0.0034333	11.73	0.001	15.9
Interaction	0.0043111	4	0.0010778	3.68	0.023	7.9
Error	0.0052667	18	0.0002926			19.4
Total	0.0394667	26				

Table 4: Analysis of variance for F_{da} of drilling process.

Figure 1: Mean F_{da} versus drilling parameters.

Fig. 2 shows scanned images of drilled specimens at the exit side. As seen in the figure, by increasing the feed rate and decreasing the spindle speed, adjusted delamination factor increases. By increasing the feed rate, the drilling process behavior will approach impact of a conic indenter tip on a composite plate. Because there is not enough time for the cutting operation and chip formation, the drill penetrates the laminate by punching. This concentrated force produces greater bending and consequently results in more interlaminar crack growth. It seems that spindle speed has an insignificant effect on adjusted delamination factor. By increasing the spindle speed to high speed drilling, material behavior changes. Karnik et al. [25] reported that when feed rate is kept at a lower value, minimum delamination can be achieved in the higher speed range. This may be attributed to the matrix softening at elevated temperatures.

Figure 2: Scanned images of drilled specimens at the exit side.

The interaction between feed rate and spindle speed is shown in Fig. 3(a). When the feed rate is kept low, minimum delamination is achieved in higher spindle speeds. This is mainly due to the softening of the matrix at higher temperatures. Fig. 3(a) indicates that the feed rate of 31.5 mm/min and spindle speed of 1000 rpm are the best choices to minimize delamination. To help visualize the interaction between feed rate and spindle speed, the related counter plot is shown in Fig. 3(b). According to the figure, at high feed rate and low spindle speed (lower right corner of the diagram) delamination is critical.

Figure 3: The interaction between feed rate and spindle speed, (b) the counter plot of the F_{da} .

Before the conclusions from the analysis of variance are adopted, the adequacy of the underlying model should be checked. The primary diagnostic tool is residual analysis. The residuals from the F_{da} data in drilling process are shown in the Fig. 4. The normal probability plot of these residuals does not reveal anything particularly troublesome, although the largest positive residual (Test 6, replicate 3) does stand out somewhat from the others. The standardized value of this residual is 2.3, and this is the only residual whose absolute value is larger than 2. The residual versus fitted values plot indicates no particular tendency for the variance of the residuals. A check of the normality assumption could be made by plotting a histogram of the residuals. The residual histogram plot shows a normal distribution centered at zero. This means that the model is adequate and basic assumptions are not violated.

Figure 4: Residual Plots for F_{da} in drilling process.

Fig. 5(a) and Fig. 5(b) plot the residual versus feed rate and spindle speed, respectively. Both plots indicate mild inequality of variance. As observed with increasing spindle speed, variance of residuals increases. The treatment combination of 63 mm/min and 1000 rpm has larger variance than the others, which is responsible for the inequality of variance.

Figure 5: Plot of standardized residuals versus (a) feed rate, (b) spindle speed.

In order to make a model relating F_{da} to feed rate and spindle speed, second order linear regression was used. Eq. (4) shows this relation. It should be noted that this is true for the values within the ranges of experiment. Fig. 6 shows response surface of this model.

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_{da} &= 0.9656 + 0.003441 f + 0.00001144 N - 0.00001429 f^2 \\
 &\quad - 0.0000007228 fN - 0.0000000874 N^2 \\
 R^2 &= 0.7996 \quad R_{adj}^2 = 0.7519
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

Figure 6: The response surface of second order linear regression for F_{da} .

To compare the extent of the damage in the drilling process and quasi-static penetration, adjusted delamination factor versus feed rate is shown in Fig. 7. From figure, a significant difference in adjusted delamination factor for drilled and penetrated specimens can be observed so that the average value of delamination for each level in quasi-static penetration is about two times greater than drilling process. Similar to drilling process, delaminated area increases as feed rate increases in quasi-static penetration. To visualize this rise, scanned images delaminated specimens in terms of the feed rate at the exit side is shown in Fig. 8. Moreover, it seems feed rate has a bigger effect in penetration process; because delamination factor variations from one level to a higher level are greater in penetration process in comparison to drilling process. This is mainly because of other governing factors in drilling process such as spindle speed.

Figure 7: Comparison of F_{da} in drilling process and quasi-static penetration.

Figure8: Scanned images of penetrated specimens at the exit side.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the effect of machining parameters, feed rate and spindle speed, on delamination in drilling process and quasi-static penetration were investigated. The results are summarized below:

Optimum cutting condition for minimum delamination was determined based on analysis of variance. A correlation between feed rate and spindle speed with the delamination factor was established by second order linear regression. According to the results, delamination increased with feed rate; whereas it decreased with spindle speed. Finally, a comparison between the delamination in drilling process and quasi-static penetration by conical-nosed projectile was made. According to the results, the difference is significant so that the average value of delamination for each level in quasi-static penetration is about two times greater than drilling process.

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